

An assessment methodology for tunnelling beneath bridges considering soil–structure interaction

Eugene K. L. Wong^a, Andrea Franza^{b,*}, Peter Hewitt^c, Giulia M. B. Viggiani^d

^a Development Bureau, Government of Hong Kong S.A.R., China. Formerly Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, UK

^b Department of Civil and Architectural Engineering, Aarhus University, Denmark

^c Geo-environmental Engineering, Laing O'Rourke, UK

^d Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, UK

Abstract

The construction of the Tideway Tunnel in London induced ground movements that affected several arch bridges along the River Thames. This study examines the responses of the Grosvenor Bridge and Putney Bridge to tunnelling-induced displacements, with a focus on soil-structure interaction (SSI) and on the relationship between foundation displacements and greenfield predictions. Coupled finite element (FE) analyses and two-stage analysis methods (TSAM) are compared, supported by some field data. The bridges are modelled as elastic frames. The equivalence between plane-strain and three-dimensional FE models is investigated, while the effectiveness of TSAM using spring-based soil-foundation models (derived from half-space theory) of varying complexity is evaluated. From the comparison with monitoring data and FE results, TSAM is shown to be practical and reliable for assessing tunnel-induced effects on bridges, including during transient conditions such as TBM approach. Results highlight the contrasting SSI response of flexible (steel) and stiff (masonry) arch bridges: while using full greenfield movements or scaling them down by some reduction factor may reasonably inform the response of flexible structures, the behaviour of stiffer systems will be markedly different as SSI significantly alters deformation mechanisms. Since the bridge response depends on the relative bridge-foundation-soil stiffness, it is recommended in all cases to perform interaction analyses from the early design stages. A workflow using TSAM is proposed to guide early-stage design assessments, integrating salient structural and geotechnical considerations.

Keywords: tunnelling, ground movements, bridge, soil-structure interaction, elastic solutions

1 Highlights

- 2 • Tunnel-soil-bridge interaction modelling: two case studies
- 3 • Two-stage analysis method (TSAM) benchmarked against
- 4 3D and plane-strain FE models
- 5 • Approach for reducing 3D structures into plane-strain
- 6 model and its limitations
- 7 • Bridge stiffness critically influences deformation and in-
- 8 ternal force distribution
- 9 • Practical workflow proposed for early-stage soil-structure
- 10 interaction (SSI) assessment using TSAM

*Corresponding author

Email address: anfr@cae.au.dk (Andrea Franza)

11 1. Introduction

12 In urban areas, bored tunnelling is a common solution to meet
13 growing demand for transportation and utility infrastructure.
14 Assessing the impact of tunnelling-induced ground movements
15 remains a critical challenge for engineers and asset owners. Al-
16 though case studies have highlighted the impact of excavation-
17 induced ground movements on piles and some bridges with
18 deep foundations (*e.g.* Cheng et al., 2007; Yoo, 2013; Yoo and
19 Abbas, 2021; Yang et al., 2025), there is no well-established
20 methodology for analysing tunnel-soil-bridge interaction in the
21 case of shallow foundations. To address this shortcoming, this
22 paper builds upon the experience from the Thames Tideway
23 project. Commencing operation in 2025, the project involved a
24 25 km-long large-diameter tunnel (8.84 m cutting diameter) ex-
25 cavated under the River Thames to intercept, store, and convey
26 sewage in order to upgrade London’s sewer system. This tunnel
27 passed beneath several bridges, most of which are arch bridges,
28 including the Putney Bridge (a heritage masonry structure) and
29 Blackfriars Bridge (a modern steel-concrete structure).

30 The Planning Inspectorate publicly released the technical re-
31 ports compiled to assess the effects of Thames Tideway tun-
32 nelling on bridges, which provided a useful reflection of cur-
33 rent engineering practices. Typically, as a first step, uncoupled
34 analyses are performed in which greenfield tunnelling move-
35 ments, whether determined from empirical formulae or numeri-
36 cal analyses, are imposed on bridge foundations; the result-
37 ing structural distortions are then calculated (*e.g.* Thames Wa-
38 ter Utilities Limited, 2013b,c). Where soil-structure interac-
39 tion (SSI) effects are considered, plane-strain (PS) numerical
40 analyses incorporating selected structural elements are carried
41 out by geotechnical engineers; the computed foundation dis-
42 placements from these PS models are then passed to structural
43 engineers, who apply them as base boundary conditions in de-
44 tailed three-dimensional (3D) superstructure models, to analyse
45 induced internal forces in structural members (*e.g.* Thames Wa-
46 ter Utilities Limited, 2012, 2013d). This change of boundary
47 conditions between two- and three-dimensional models is in-
48 evitably subject to engineering judgement and approximations.
49 Impact assessments often assume that bridge foundations fol-
50 low greenfield displacement profiles, neglecting the influence
51 of existing structures. This disregards the effects of SSI and
52 overlooks the ability of the superstructure stiffness in modifying
53 the foundation response. While straightforward, this approach
54 can result in overly conservative or inaccurate estimates, as ex-
55 plored in this study.

56 The reliance on greenfield methods in bridge assessments de-
57 rives directly from the framework developed for buildings (*e.g.*
58 [Mair et al., 1996](#); [Crossrail, 2008](#); [Schoor et al., 2021](#)). In
59 the case of buildings, well-established procedures link defor-
60 mation parameters from greenfield displacements at foundation
61 level to damage categories, supported by extensive literature
62 (*e.g.* [Franzius et al., 2006](#); [Dimmock and Mair, 2008](#); [Farrell
63 et al., 2014](#); [Giardina et al., 2015](#); [Boldini et al., 2021](#)). How-
64 ever, tunnel-bridge interaction remains less well-studied, possi-
65 bly because the diversity of structural forms and configurations
66 defies generalisation. [Franza and DeJong \(2019\)](#) conceptually

67 evaluated the effects of tunnelling-induced movements on sim-
68 ple bridges on separate footings for orthogonal arrangements
69 of piers and decks (modelled as beam elements), using elastic
70 soil-frame interaction analyses. Their results highlighted that
71 the qualitative distribution of tunnelling-induced movements of
72 the foundation is modified compared with greenfield shapes as
73 a result of frame action, which is not readily accounted for
74 by a modification factor. A similar observation was made for
75 the Grosvenor Bridge in the study by [Faherty et al. \(2022\)](#).
76 Their parametric study of steel arch bridges highlighted the
77 challenges of generalising risk assessment protocols; bridge re-
78 sponses to ground movements are highly dependent on struc-
79 tural factors such as roller bearing travel, internal partial hinges
80 and expansion joints — details that are often difficult to cap-
81 ture in geotechnical models. This intrinsic structural complex-
82 ity also supports the suggestion that damage criteria for bridges
83 subjected to foundation movements are not well established.
84 For instance, the [Federal Highway Administration \(1985\)](#) pro-
85 posed some thresholds for the tolerable longitudinal angular
86 distortion (ratio of differential settlement to span length) for
87 bridges of different materials and construction; however, this
88 may not adequately account for excavation-induced horizontal
89 movements. Furthermore, it is not straightforward to corre-
90 late structural damage with computed internal forces. Conse-
91 quently, structural engineers frequently resort to detailed nu-
92 merical analysis to assess the structural response of existing
93 bridges to tunnel construction, which are informed by the ex-
94 pected magnitude and shape of tunnelling-induced foundation
95 movements provided by geotechnical engineers, which may or
96 may not consider SSI. The research questions of what are ade-
97 quate modelling strategies for risk assessments and their poten-
98 tial pitfalls arise.

99 This paper compares different tunnel-soil-structure interac-
100 tion approaches, evaluating their strengths and limitations for
101 varying levels of complexity of the soil-foundation system.
102 First, the Grosvenor Bridge and the Putney Bridge case stud-
103 ies are presented along with an overview of the modelling
104 approaches used. Second, the measured movements of the
105 Grosvenor Bridge from the Tideway Tunnel construction are
106 examined, building on [Wong \(2019\)](#) and [Faherty et al. \(2022\)](#);
107 the short-term, in-plane, steady-state bridge deformations are
108 considered. Predictions from plane-strain finite element (PSFE)
109 analyses using a simple soil constitutive model in total stress
110 are presented; a procedure to define an equivalent plane-strain
111 foundation to capture the flexibility associated with the actual
112 three-dimensional geometry is proposed. Third, the study com-
113 pares field and numerical FE results with elastic SSI models
114 following the two-stage analysis method (TSAM) using dif-
115 ferent representations based on lumped springs: fully-coupled
116 (half-space theory), locally-coupled (spatially decoupled with
117 local roto-translational coupling), and decoupled (spatially de-
118 coupled without roto-translational coupling). Fourth, a TSAM
119 analysis of the response of the Putney Bridge to tunnelling is
120 presented; results highlight the requirements, versatility, and
121 advantages of spring-based modelling approach for a relatively
122 stiff bridge in which SSI effects are expected to be significant.
123 Finally, a discussion on how spring-based two-stage modelling

124 could be used for studying the effects of transient ground move-
 125 ments in 3D by using a 3D TSAM model of the Grosvenor
 126 Bridge subjected to an advancing tunnel excavation is provided;
 127 the results are compared with field observations. Guidance is
 128 also given on how to carry out an integrated analysis that ac-
 129 counts for both tunnelling and soil-foundation interaction.

130 2. Case studies

131 2.1. Grosvenor Bridge

132 The Grosvenor Bridge is located in central London. It is a
 133 steel railway arch bridge crossing the River Thames between
 134 Pimlico and Battersea, near Victoria Station. It supports railway
 135 tracks that carry both passenger and freight traffic. The bridge
 136 is supported by masonry piers embedded in London Clay. The
 137 Thames Tideway Tunnel passed under the Grosvenor Bridge at
 138 a position between its South and Centre Piers (Fig. 1).

139 The bridge was originally constructed in the second half of
 140 the 1800s and it underwent several phases of widening, modifi-
 141 cation, and partial reconstruction between 1865 and 1967 (Wil-
 142 son, 1868; Fox, 1868; Kerensky and Partridge, 1967; Keren-
 143 sky et al., 1967). The present structure consists of four spans,
 144 each ranging from 55 to 57 m, with a 50 m wide deck sup-
 145 ported by ten parallel, structurally separate but identical, steel
 146 arch frames. Each frame is made of two arch ribs with rectan-
 147 gular hollow cross-sections. The arches support the deck via
 148 spandrel posts. The deck consists of 15.9 mm thick mild steel
 149 plates, supported by inverted Universal-T sections. The arches
 150 are pin-connected at each pier and connected monolithically
 151 with the deck at mid-span. The deck is simply supported at
 152 the piers. The piers are made of masonry encased in reinforced
 153 concrete and are embedded in London Clay. Fig. 2 shows the
 154 mechanical model of the bridge as a plane frame and indicates
 155 the positions of the targets used to monitor the displacements of
 156 the bridge during excavation of the tunnel.

157 The westbound earth pressure balance tunnel boring machine
 158 (EPB TBM) with an external diameter of 8.84 m was launched
 159 from a shaft on Kirtling Street in January 2019. It passed un-
 160 derneath the Grosvenor Bridge over five days in March 2019.
 161 Monitoring data from the Thames Tideway Tunnel project, in-
 162 cluding settlement, horizontal movements and displacements of
 163 the bridge deck provide a reference to validate model predic-
 164 tions.

165 The tunnel was excavated at a depth of approximately 34 m
 166 below the riverbed, primarily through London Clay, but its in-
 167 vert was close to or within the Lambeth Group (Thames Wa-
 168 ter Utilities Limited, 2013a,d). At this location, the Lambeth
 169 Group comprises Lower Shelly Clays and Upper Mottled
 170 Clays of the Woolwich and Reading Formations. Near
 171 Grosvenor Bridge, the geotechnical investigations by Skemp-
 172 ton and Henkel (1957) and Kerensky et al. (1967) provided the
 173 undrained shear strength profile with depth below the London
 174 Clay horizon, as shown in Fig. 3.

175 At the foundation base level of the Grosvenor Bridge, ap-
 176 proximately 4 m into the London Clay, the undrained shear
 177 strength is in the range 100–200 kPa. At the small strain lev-
 178 els relevant for settlement predictions, the undrained Young's

Figure 1. Layout of Grosvenor Bridge showing (a) general view and (b) relative positions of bridge and tunnel

Figure 2. Plane-frame model of Grosvenor Bridge: structural members and internal connections

179 modulus E_u of London Clay is estimated as 500–800 S_u , con-
 180 sidering its correlation to the plasticity index and the overcon-
 181 solidation ratio (Viggiani, 1999). These estimates align with
 182 the values reported by Withers et al. (2001) who found E_u/S_u
 183 in the range 500–1500 at a strain level of 0.01%, and also sug-
 184 gested that E_u exceeds 75 MPa. For the numerical analyses in
 185 this paper, we adopt the Young's modulus value suggested by
 186 Kerensky and Partridge (1967), $E_u = 105$ MPa (1000 tons/ft²),
 187 based on the observations from a nearby building construction
 188 site. During the 1966–67 reconstruction of the bridge, the same
 189 Young's modulus value was used to estimate the immediate set-
 190 tlement of its piers, showing very good agreement with field
 191 observations.

192 Before reaching the Grosvenor Bridge, the Tideway TBM
 193 passed beneath three utility tunnels, where the average volume
 194 loss was back-calculated as 0.9% (Wong, 2019). In the absence

Figure 3. Undrained shear strength of London Clay near Grosvenor Bridge

of settlement measurements along a full greenfield transverse cross-section, a volume loss value V_L of 1% was assumed as a first approximation.

2.2. Putney Bridge

The Putney Bridge is a Grade II listed masonry arch bridge located in southwest London, connecting Putney and Fulham across the River Thames. Originally constructed between 1882 and 1886, it consists of five segmental stone and granite arches, with spans ranging from approximately 34 m to 44 m and arch rise of 5 m to 6 m. The structure was widened in 1933, with a 9.14 m wide extension on the downstream side using mass concrete, while maintaining the original visual appearance. The concrete deck is supported by longitudinal spandrel walls constructed of brick for the original structure and mass concrete for the extension portion, with stone slabs spanning between spandrels having no backfill between them. The arches are constructed from granite blocks (with thickness of 1.25 m) and bear directly onto the mass concrete piers and abutments. The bridge does not include bearings or movement joints.

The Thames Tideway TBM passed beneath the southern intermediate span of the Putney Bridge, with a tunnel axis depth of 25.3 m below riverbed level (neglecting the presence of 1 m thick alluvium layer). This southern intermediate span has a clear span of 39.4 m and height (rise) of 5.4 m. The founding soil consists of London clay up to a depth of about 15 m from the invert depth. The foundations have a width of 10.3 m (in direction transverse to tunnel axis) and length of 36 m (in direction along tunnel axis), and are embedded about 6.1 m into London Clay; the embedment is approximately 25% of the tunnel axis depth. The pier height from the founding level to the lower point of the arch is approx. 8.2 m while pier transverse width is 5.6 m. A tunnelling volume loss of 1% was assumed, and the undrained Young's modulus of the London Clay was taken as 105 MPa as for the Grosvenor Bridge, an order of magnitude greater than the value adopted in Tideway Project's

assessment report for Putney Bridge (Thames Water Utilities Limited, 2012).

Making reference to Thames Water Utilities Limited (2012), we constructed a plane-frame numerical model for the bridge superstructure. Table 1 summarises the axial and bending stiffness of beam elements adopted for the combined arches and spandrels, the deck and the piers, for the two bridges examined in this paper.

Figure 4. Putney Bridge (photo courtesy of Wandsworth Council, London)

Figure 5. Plane-frame model of Putney Bridge

Table 1. Cross sectional properties of main structural members in numerical models

Structural member	Grosvenor Bridge	Putney Bridge
Arch	$I = 0.298 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 1.32 \text{ m}^2$	$I = 202 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 72.2 \text{ m}^2$
Deck	$I = 0.005 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 0.761 \text{ m}^2$	$I = 6.32 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 34.5 \text{ m}^2$
Pier	$I = 12864 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 898 \text{ m}^2$	$I = 3278 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 371 \text{ m}^2$
Spandrels	$I = 0.004 \text{ m}^4$ $A = 0.095 \text{ m}^2$	(Incorporated in arch)

3. Interaction models

3.1. Two-stage analysis method (TSAM)

Two-stage elastic models have been applied in the literature to study SSI involving pipelines and buildings affected by tunnelling (e.g. Klar et al., 2005; Franza and DeJong, 2019). The first stage of the analysis involves predicting greenfield displacements at the foundation level, which serve as the primary tunnelling-related input in TSAM. In the second stage, the interaction problem is solved by incorporating structure-foundation

247 stiffness and applying the greenfield-equivalent set of forces
 248 that would displace the soil-foundation by the greenfield move-
 249 ments. In this paper, linear elastic two-stage interaction models
 250 are adopted for the bridge problems, with preliminary results
 251 reported in Wong et al. (2021).

252 Greenfield movements at the foundation level can be esti-
 253 mated using semi-empirical relationships, analytical solutions
 254 or numerical methods. In this paper, greenfield displacements
 255 in the vertical and horizontal directions are estimated using the
 256 empirical method in Wong et al. (2025). Briefly, the transverse
 257 settlement profile in clay follows a Gaussian distribution (Peck,
 258 1969; Mair and Taylor, 1997), while the expression from Mair
 259 et al. (1993) is selected to describe the linear variation of the in-
 260 flexion point offset with depth; horizontal movements are cal-
 261 culated from settlements considering the variation of the focus
 262 point of the total displacement vector with transverse offset and
 263 depth. Contrary to the assumption that at any given depth the
 264 displacement vectors point towards a unique point, Wong et al.
 265 (2025) demonstrated that for case histories of tunnel excava-
 266 tions in fine-grained soils, the vector focus at the ground surface
 267 is above the tunnel centre and its depth becomes shallower with
 268 increasing transverse distance from the tunnel centre-line; be-
 269 low a depth of 20% the tunnel axis depth, the focus point depth
 270 is assumed to be at 1.54 times the tunnel depth.

271 For the greenfield stage 1, Eq. (1)–(2) describe the steady-
 272 state settlement w as a standard Gaussian curve.

$$w = w_{\max} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2i^2}\right); \quad w_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{32}} \frac{V_L D_t^2}{i} \quad (1)$$

$$i = 0.5z_t - 0.325z \quad (2)$$

273 where w is the settlement at a transverse horizontal distance x
 274 from the tunnel axis, w_{\max} is the maximum centre-line settle-
 275 ment, i is the horizontal distance of the point of inflexion from
 276 the tunnel axis, V_L is the volume loss, expressed as a percentage
 277 of the nominal volume of the tunnel of diameter D_t , and z_t is
 278 the depth of the tunnel axis.

279 The transverse horizontal displacement u at distance x from
 280 the tunnel axis and at depth z can be expressed as a function
 281 of the settlement w at the same location, and of the normalised
 282 depth of the focus point $h = z_f/z_t$, which in turn is a function
 283 of the normalised depth z/z_t and normalised offset x/i .

$$u = -w \frac{x}{h z_t - z} \quad (3)$$

where:

$$h = h_0 = \frac{3.59}{4.43 + \exp\left(\frac{x^2}{1.3i^2}\right)} \quad \text{when } z = 0; \quad (4a)$$

$$h = (h_0 - 1.54) \left(1 - \frac{z}{0.2z_t}\right) + 1.54 \quad \text{when } 0 < \frac{z}{z_t} < 0.2; \quad (4b)$$

$$h = 1.54 \quad \text{when } \frac{z}{z_t} \geq 0.2 \quad (4c)$$

284 If $h = 1$, the displacement vectors point towards the tunnel
 285 centre. Eq. (4) establishes that, near the ground surface, the

286 normalised focus depth $h < 1$ close to the centre-line and h
 287 reduces with the normalised offset x/i . In this paper, Eq. (1)–(4)
 288 were applied considering the ground surface horizon to be at
 289 the foundation level.

290 In stage 2, the bridge response to tunnelling is studied by
 291 modelling the superstructure as a plane frame resting on foot-
 292 ings tied to the spring-based ground model (consisting of ei-
 293 ther fully-coupled, locally-coupled, or decoupled springs as dis-
 294 cussed below). Fig. 6 shows the interaction model for the bridge
 295 schematised as either a plane or three-dimensional frame. As
 296 the interaction model is linear elastic, the foundation maintains
 297 displacement compatibility between the soil and the footings.
 298 The pier bases were assumed to be rigid; thus, the foundations
 299 and the displacements of the foundation soil were described by
 300 single nodes at the centres of the footing footprints, collectively
 301 referred to as the *foundation master-nodes*. Tunnelling effects
 302 were modelled by applying an equivalent set of forces that dis-
 303 place the spring foundation model alone by the greenfield dis-
 304 placements, including greenfield rotations when appropriate (as
 305 discussed later).

Figure 6. Interactive springs adopted in two-stage elastic solution analysing plane frame in $x - z$ plane under steady-state tunnelling conditions

The interaction problem is solved with the finite element method. The equilibrium equation in matrix form describing the frame displacement under the effects of tunnelling is:

$$(\mathbf{K}_{st} + \mathbf{K}_f) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{p}_{gf} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_f = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{K}_s \mathbf{A} \quad (6)$$

306 where \mathbf{K}_{st} and \mathbf{K}_f are the structure and the foundation (soil-
 307 footing system) stiffness matrix, respectively, and \mathbf{u} is the dis-
 308 placement vector describing translational and rotational degrees
 309 of freedom of the structure (including superstructure and pier
 310 base points); for a plane frame, the translational degrees of free-
 311 dom in the x and z directions and the rotations in the $x - z$ plane
 312 are considered; \mathbf{A} is a kinematic constraint matrix relating the
 313 translational and rotational degrees of freedom of the founda-
 314 tion master-nodes to the translational degrees of freedom of the
 315 soil underneath the foundation footprint: *i.e.* as the footing is
 316 assumed to be rigid, compatibility imposed via \mathbf{A} requires that
 317 the displacements of the soil at the footing should be a linear
 318 function of the displacements of the pier base points (later de-
 319 tailed in the text); \mathbf{K}_s is the soil stiffness matrix (defined with
 320 respect to all nodes at the soil-footings interface); \mathbf{p}_{gf} is the vec-
 321 tor of the equivalent greenfield tunnelling-induced forces acting

322 on the foundation.

323 As shown in Fig. 6, the superstructure is discretised into finite
324 elements. The superstructure stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_{st} is obtained
325 by assembling (i) Euler-Bernoulli beams for the straight
326 steel members rigid in shear, (ii) Timoshenko beams for the stiff
327 concrete piers (Friedman and Kosmatka, 1993) and (iii) curved
328 Euler-Bernoulli beams for the arches (Litewka and Rakowski,
329 1997) while (iv) the rigid footings were modelled by introduc-
330 ing the kinematic constraint matrix discussed above. All internal
331 hinges and rollers (as illustrated in Fig. 2) were duly consid-
332 ered by manipulating the finite element stiffness matrix to
333 account for the release of the relevant internal forces. Full de-
334 tails of the stiffness matrix are documented in Wong (2019) and
335 Wong et al. (2021).

336 To establish the soil stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_s , the soil tied to the
337 footing interface was discretised into a grid of nodes (each hav-
338 ing three translational degrees of freedom), whose displacement
339 vector \mathbf{u}_s is linked to the superstructure by the kinematic con-
340 straint as $\mathbf{u}_s = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{u}$. From the kinematic constraint matrix,
341 it follows that \mathbf{K}_f is a condensed stiffness matrix of \mathbf{K}_s with
342 respect to the degrees of freedom at the centroids of the pier
343 bases. Therefore, the foundation system comprising soil and
344 rigid footings as described by \mathbf{K}_f consists of roto-translational
345 springs, all lumped at the bases of the piers as shown in Fig. 6
346 via the kinematic constraint matrix. Interaction terms of these
347 foundation springs (*i.e.* off-diagonal terms of \mathbf{K}_f) depend on
348 the adopted model as follows:

- 349 • *Fully-coupled* (FC) springs: linear elastic half-space the-
350 ory was used for the soil, resulting in a fully populated
351 stiffness matrix, coupling all roto-translational behaviour
352 across all footings. The soil flexibility matrix was ob-
353 tained from the Boussinesq-Cerruti solution (Love, 1927;
354 Li and Berger, 2001) and the integrated Mindlin's solu-
355 tion of a uniformly loaded rectangular area (Cheung and
356 Nag, 1968) (see Appendix A: Formulation of soil stiffness
357 matrix for fully-coupled (FC) springs solution). The em-
358 bedment of the footings was not taken into account. For a
359 structure consisting of multiple individual footings, these
360 were discretised into an array of n nodes distributed below
361 the footprint whose three translational dofs are collected
362 in \mathbf{u}_s , following the procedure outlined above to generate
363 a $3n \times 3n$ soil stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_s . This enables the cou-
364 pling between different footings across the surface of the
365 soil.
- 366 • *Locally-coupled* (LC) springs: the diagonal terms and lo-
367 cal roto-translational terms of each footing were accounted
368 for but no interaction between different piers was consid-
369 ered. This was formulated in the same manner as the FC
370 springs from Love (1927) and Cheung and Nag (1968),
371 but by discretising a single footing instead of all the foot-
372 ings across the continuum while neglecting the embed-
373 ment of the footings (LC1 springs). Alternatively, the roto-
374 translation stiffness of isolated, rigid, embedded/surface
375 footings on the half-space or a compressible layer of finite
376 depth could be defined based on semi-empirical formu-
377 lae (Pais and Kausel, 1988; Gazetas, 1991a,b) (LC2

378 springs; see Appendix B: Formulation of soil stiffness ma-
379 trix for decoupled (DC) or locally-coupled (LC2) springs
380 solution).

- *Decoupled* (DC) springs: a diagonal stiffness matrix was
used, with springs that only react to local loads in their
directions. The spring constants were obtained from the
diagonal terms of the LC2 stiffness matrix.

385 For practical applications, the stiffness values of locally-
386 coupled and decoupled foundation springs can be readily cal-
387 culated either from the literature for a given foundation layout
388 (footing length, width, embedment, etc) or from 3D finite el-
389 ement analyses (calculating the load-displacement relationship
390 at the master-node of a footing resting on linear elastic mate-
391 rial).

392 The vector of tunnelling-induced forces \mathbf{p}_{gf} was computed
393 from the vector of greenfield displacements $\mathbf{u}_{s,gf}$ at foundation
394 nodes, established using empirical formulae or numerical re-
395 sults. For FC and LC1 springs, $\mathbf{p}_{gf} = \mathbf{A}^T \mathbf{K}_s \mathbf{u}_{s,gf}$, derived from
396 the vertical and horizontal greenfield displacements at the soil-
397 footing interface. For LC2 or DC springs, $\mathbf{p}_{gf} = \mathbf{K}_f \mathbf{u}_{gf}$; in addi-
398 tion to vertical and horizontal displacements, \mathbf{u}_{gf} also contains
399 greenfield rotations, which were computed as the first derivative
400 of the greenfield settlement profile at the footing centroids.

401 The TSAM analyses adopting linear elastic frames for the
402 superstructure (see Fig. 2 and 5) were carried out for the
403 Grosvenor and Putney Bridges. Note that, if nonlinear struc-
404 tural behaviour is of interest, the linear spring-based ground
405 models described above could all be implemented within com-
406 mercial structural computer programs for routine applications;
407 in particular, LC and DC springs would be straightforward to
408 calibrate and implement.

409 3.2. Equivalence between 3D and PS foundations in FE analy- 410 ses

411 Geotechnical plane-strain analyses are frequently used for
412 simplicity and efficiency. There are different methods to
413 achieve the required equivalence between the plane-strain
414 model and the actual three dimensional problem, while main-
415 taining the relative soil-to-structure stiffness. The equivalence
416 is achieved either by scaling the stiffness and the weight of the
417 structure (*e.g.* Rampello et al., 2012) or by modifying the foun-
418 dation dimensions or by a combination of the two (*e.g.* Callisto
419 et al., 2013; Rampello et al., 2014) depending on the problem
420 at hand. In fact, the deformability (*i.e.* the displacement un-
421 der unit external load) of a foundation system (consisting of
422 soil and footings) in plane-strain may be significantly differ-
423 ent from that of a three-dimensional footing: an infinite strip
424 foundation is more flexible than a rectangular footprint for a
425 given transverse width and unit external load per longitudinal
426 length (Pais and Kausel, 1988; Dempsey and Li, 1989; Gaze-
427 tas, 1991a,b). In other words, the foundation displacements and
428 the rotation of an infinite strip footing are larger than those of
429 a three-dimensional rectangular footing under identical loads
430 per longitudinal length (longitudinal referring to out-of-plane
431 direction of bridge structure, parallel to direction of tunnel ad-
432 vancement).

433 If both the structure and the foundation behaviour are de-
 434 scribed using stiffness matrices condensed with respect to the
 435 degrees of freedom of the foundation (pier base), the equi-
 436 librium equation of a 3D structure resting on a linear elastic
 437 ground model requires that:

$$(\mathbf{K}_{st,3D} + \mathbf{K}_{f,3D}) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{K}_{f,3D} \mathbf{u}_{gf} \quad (7)$$

438 where $\mathbf{K}_{st,3D}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{f,3D}$ are the structure and foundation stiffness
 439 matrices of the 3D structure.

440 A plane-strain (PS) model may be considered equivalent to
 441 the 3D one when, for a given greenfield input \mathbf{u}_{gf} , it yields the
 442 same interaction outcome \mathbf{u} as the 3D model. The equivalence
 443 can be achieved either by scaling the stiffness of the structure
 444 (*Method A*) or by modifying the foundation layout while keep-
 445 ing the mechanical properties of the structure (*Method B*). Re-
 446 gardless of the approach adopted, as discussed later, a perfect
 447 equivalence between PS and 3D models cannot be achieved by
 448 either method; engineering judgment is thus needed to define
 449 equivalent plane-strain models. TSAM is well-suited to 3D
 450 analysis (*e.g.* plane/3D frame on 3D foundation), while the
 451 problem of equivalence arises when adopting PS finite element
 452 coupled numerical analyses.

453 3.2.1. Method A – scaling the structure

If the transverse width B of the foundation in the PS model
 is set to be the same as the actual width B_0 in the 3D problem,
 it follows that the 3D foundation stiffness can be expressed as a
 function of the PS stiffness matrix:

$$L_0^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{f,3D} = \mathbf{M} \mathbf{K}_{f,PS} \quad (8)$$

454 where L_0 is the length of the foundation in the out-of-plane di-
 455 rection while \mathbf{M} is the matrix describing the relationship be-
 456 tween $\mathbf{K}_{f,3D}$ and $\mathbf{K}_{f,PS}$ per unit longitudinal length. By manip-
 457 ulating Eq. (7) and (8), it follows that the equivalent PS model
 458 is:

$$(\mathbf{K}_{st,PS}^* + \mathbf{K}_{f,PS}) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{K}_{f,PS} \mathbf{u}_{gf} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{st,PS}^* = \mathbf{M}^{-1} L_0^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{st,3D} \quad (10)$$

which is obtained by scaling the stiffness matrix of the struc-
 ture in the 2D model. The superscript * denotes the equivalent
 stiffness obtained by scaling. To simplify the scaling problem,
 it may be assumed that all degrees of freedom of the 2D and 3D
 foundation stiffness matrices scale equally and independently,
 in other words, \mathbf{M} is a scalar. Under this assumption:

$$\mathbf{K}_{st,PS}^* \approx (L_0 \cdot m)^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{st,3D} \quad (11)$$

459 Note that $m \geq 1$ given that an infinite strip footing is less stiff
 460 than a rectangular footing under identical loads per unit longi-
 461 tudinal length. Eq. (11) may be practically implemented in nu-
 462 merical models by dividing the Young's modulus of the struc-
 463 ture by m while keeping the actual foundation width B_0 .

464 3.2.2. Method B – scaling the foundation

465 An alternative approach is to increase the PS foundation
 466 width B from the 3D value B_0 to achieve equivalence. In this
 467 way, the PS foundation matrix is approximately the 3D matrix
 468 divided by L_0 while the PS structure is simply obtained as a unit
 469 slice of the full structure. It follows that

$$(\mathbf{K}_{st,PS} + \mathbf{K}_{f,PS}^*) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{K}_{f,PS}^* \mathbf{u}_{gf} \quad (12)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{f,PS}^* \approx L_0^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{f,3D} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{st,PS} = L_0^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{st,3D} \quad (14)$$

When adopting different transverse widths B for PS and 3D
 models, the ratio between 3D and PS foundation stiffness ma-
 trices can be quantified by the term

$$\mathbf{R} = L_0 \mathbf{K}_{f,3D}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{f,PS}^* \quad (15)$$

470 By definition, an effective equivalence achieved by scaling the
 471 foundation (see Eq. 15) is obtained when \mathbf{R} is the identity ma-
 472 trix (all diagonal elements R_{ii} are as close as possible to unity).
 473 However, it is impossible to satisfy $R_{ii} = 1$ for all elements be-
 474 cause of the different ratios between PS and 3D stiffness values
 475 depending on the load directions/degrees of freedom.

476 The equivalence of a plane-strain analysis is addressed in the
 477 subsequent section. In contrast, there is no need to consider
 478 equivalence in the TSAM, given that the soil stiffness matrix is
 479 obtained from 3D theories in the first place.

480 3.3. Plane-strain (PSFE) and three-dimensional (3DFE) cou- 481 pled finite element models

482 Two coupled numerical analysis methods were used in this
 483 study to study the interaction between the Tideway Tunnel
 484 and Grosvenor Bridge in the short term: plane-strain finite
 485 element (PSFE) and three-dimensional finite element (3DFE)
 486 models for which the programs PLAXIS 2D (version 20) and
 487 PLAXIS 3D (version 17) were used, respectively.

488 The 3DFE model acts as a benchmark for PSFE and spring-
 489 based TSAM models; therefore, the 3DFE analyses were car-
 490 ried out for short-term, steady-state tunnelling only. The plane-
 491 strain model PSFE is similar to the approach practitioners typi-
 492 cally use for tunnelling impact assessments to study foundation
 493 and superstructure steady-state movements (*e.g.* Thames Water
 494 Utilities Limited, 2012, 2013d) and it was adopted here to study
 495 the equivalence between PSFE and 3DFE interaction models by
 496 scaling the foundation length (*Method A*). The model geome-
 497 tries of both the PSFE and 3DFE models were identical: struc-
 498 tural elements of the bridge superstructure were modelled as
 499 plate elements (for PSFE) or beam elements (for 3DFE), while
 500 spandrel posts which were hinged at both ends were modelled
 501 as node-to-node anchors. On the other hand, Putney Bridge was
 502 only analysed with TSAM.

503 The steady-state condition following the complete passage of
 504 the TBM within London Clay was simulated in total stress anal-
 505 ysis. In the analysis, the bridge was assumed to be weightless
 506 as the aim of the analysis was to study the tunnelling-induced

Figure 7. Finite element models of Grosvenor Bridge and tunnel excavation: (a) plane-strain model PSFE and (b) three-dimensional model with plane frame 3DFE

507 undrained response of the soil and the bridge. The ground material was assumed to be linear elastic – perfectly plastic and follow the Tresca failure criterion. Fig. 7 shows the mesh adopted for the analysis. The bottom boundary of the ground model was taken at the bottom of the London Clay horizon, assumed to be 1 m below the invert of the tunnel, while the horizontal extent was set beyond the river banks, which were outside the tunnelling influence zone, for a total width of 270 m. The following soil properties were assumed for the ground model: $\gamma = 20 \text{ kN/m}^3$, $E_u = 150 \text{ MPa}$, $S_u = 200 \text{ kPa}$, $K_0 = 0.7$ and $\nu = 0.495$, selected with reference to assessment reports under the Tideway project. Standard boundary conditions were used (rollers on vertical boundaries, fixed bottom boundary). The model boundary, while close to the abutments of the bridge, did not affect the analysis results because the deck structure with roller connections does not transmit longitudinal loads between spans.

524 A displacement-controlled technique was used in the PSFE and 3DFE model to model tunnelling. Following Cheng et al. (2007), a technique was used in the PSFE and 3DFE analyses to model tunnelling, in which the displacements of the nodes located around the tunnel converge towards a single point on the tunnel vertical line of symmetry, generically located between the tunnel axis and the invert. The point of convergence of dis-

531 placements is close to the tunnel centre for deep tunnels, moving towards the invert for shallower tunnels. In particular, the back-analysis by Cheng et al. (2007) suggested a linear variation of the focus point with the cover-to-diameter ratio; for the Grosvenor case study this gave a focus depth at 60% the tunnel radius below the tunnel axis ($z = z_t + 0.6R$).

537 The bridge superstructure was modelled using Mindlin plate elements, with either fixed or hinged ends (Fig. 2). Their bending and axial stiffness per unit longitudinal length were obtained by dividing the actual 3D values of the stiffness EA and EI by the calibrated length of the bridge foundation in the out of plane direction $L = m L_0$, and then the contribution from the ten separate bridge frames were summed ($\sum EI/L$ and $\sum EA/L$). The Young's modulus of steel E was taken as 200 GPa. The shear stiffness GA_s was given by the equivalent rectangular cross-section used in PLAXIS and $G = 2(1+\nu)E$ (Bentley, 2020a). As the ten actual bridge frames would behave in plane-stress condition, it was necessary to prevent the Poisson's ratio from stiffening the plane-strain model by setting $\nu = 0$ (Bentley, 2020b). The footings (*i.e.* the portions of the pier below ground surface) were modelled by triangular elements (as was the soil) with the Young's modulus of concrete and masonry taken as 20 GPa.

553 To make the comparison with the PS finite element analysis more straightforward, the actual foundation width was adopted

555 ($B = B_0$) in *Method A*. To scale the footing length L from the actual length L_0 , the three degrees of freedom, namely, displacement u along x , displacement w along z and rotation about y , were individually considered. A 3D model of the actual rectangular footing was first constructed using PLAXIS 3D. Unit forces (or moment) were applied to the footing in turn and the resulting displacements were computed. Next, a PS (plane-strain) model of the same footing with the actual width B_0 was constructed using PLAXIS 2D. For each degree of freedom, the same unit forces as in the 3D case, divided by a foundation length L to obtain the loading per unit length, were applied to the PS model (Fig. 8). The calibrated foundation lengths L that gave identical displacements in the PS and 3D models for each degree of freedom were obtained (Table 2). The combinations of B and L which gave identical displacements between PS and 3D solutions are illustrated in Fig. 9, in which the shaded areas refer to a deviation within 10%. A foundation length of $L = 1.32 L_0$ ($L_0 = 60$ m) was adopted. With this geometry, the PSFE analysis should give the same horizontal footing displacement as a full 3D model while the vertical and rotational movements were within 6% of the corresponding 3D results.

Figure 8. Approach to establish equivalence between PS and 3D foundations

Figure 9. Combinations of L and B giving equivalent plane-strain and 3D finite element solutions

Table 2. Calibrated length L of footing for scaling superstructure stiffness in PSFE analysis

Degree of freedom	Calibrated footing length L^\dagger
Horizontal displacement u	80.38 m
Settlement w	71.07 m
Rotation r_y	72.86 m

† Actual footing length $L_0 = 60$ m

580 Fig. 10 compares greenfield ground movements along the horizon at the base of the foundation (approximately 4 m depth), obtained from the PSFE and 3DFE models in greenfield conditions (without the bridge), with those obtained from the empirical method of Wong et al. (2025) described earlier. All predictions assume a tunnelling volume loss of 1%.

586 FE predictions of the greenfield settlement and the gradient of the settlement trough are in excellent agreement with the empirical values at the South and Centre Piers of the Grosvenor Bridge — the two piers located within the tunnel's influence zone. This agreement is important, as these movements are the main drivers of soil-structure interaction in this case (as discussed later).

Figure 10. Greenfield movements at foundation level for tunnelling volume loss of 1%: (a) settlement and (b) transverse horizontal movement

593 However, this figure also shows that the extent of the horizontal displacement profile from the FE analyses is wider than that for the empirical curve, which affected the magnitude of horizontal movements at the South and Centre Piers, despite similar peak values. The greenfield horizontal movements from the FE analyses are larger than from the empirical predictions by about 35% and 70% at the locations of the South and Centre Piers, respectively. The FE horizontal displacement profile is wider and reduces more gradually away from the tunnel axis compared to the empirical prediction. These differences could be relevant

576 4. Results for the Grosvenor Bridge case study

577 4.1. Greenfield movements

578 Before addressing the interaction problem, greenfield movement predictions for the Grosvenor Bridge are discussed.

603 for bridge-tunnel problems with different configurations to the
 604 present case, and are later assessed with interaction analyses.
 605 Also, this highlights a key advantage of TSAM: it enables the
 606 use of specific, user-specified, realistic greenfield displacement
 607 fields, in contrast to coupled FE analyses, which may yield less
 608 representative results when simplified constitutive models (*e.g.*
 609 Tresca-type) are used to simulate the excavation process (Haji
 610 *et al.*, 2018).

611 4.2. Comparison of TSAM and FE predictions with field data

612 Table 3 summarises the tunnelling-induced displacements of
 613 the foundation master-nodes (*i.e.* at the base of the piers) along
 614 with the maximum tunnelling-induced vertical movement and
 615 internal forces in the arch directly above the excavation. In
 616 addition, Table 3 lists “greenfield uncoupled” results obtained
 617 by imposing (as displacement boundary conditions) greenfield
 618 translations and rotations to the foundation master-nodes of the
 619 plane-stress bridge frame. The deformed shape of the overall
 620 bridge obtained from the PSFE analysis is shown in Fig. 11
 621 whereas Fig. 12 compares the deformed configurations obtained
 622 from the PSFE analysis directly against the TSAM FC model
 623 (relying on fully coupled foundation springs based on
 624 half-space theory). Finally, Fig. 13 shows the horizontal and
 625 vertical components of the total displacement vector measured
 626 in the field near the top of the South Pier, together with the in-
 627 teraction results from the different interaction models.

Figure 11. Tunnelling-induced deformed configuration predicted by PSFE analysis (scale factor of 200)

628 The tunnelling-induced horizontal movement and rotation of
 629 the footings (and piers) are key to the behaviour of the bridge in
 630 this interaction problem. The footings of the South and Centre
 631 Piers tilted towards the tunnel axis following the gradient of the
 632 tunnelling settlement trough. Given the rigidity of piers, they
 633 essentially tilted as rigid bodies following the slope of the foot-
 634 ings, resulting in horizontal movements of the top of the piers
 635 towards the tunnel centre-line; this mechanism is confirmed by
 636 the field measurements shown in Fig. 13 near the top of the
 637 South Pier. As the horizontal displacement of the top of the
 638 piers is contributed by (i) the footing horizontal movements and
 639 (ii) the footing rotation multiplied by the pier height, the
 640 relatively flexible arches of the bridge span directly above the
 641 tunnel were put into compression and deflected upwards, while
 642 tension was induced in the adjacent arches. This mode of de-
 643 formation is visualised in the deformed shape of the bridge in
 644 Fig. 11 and it is the result of Grosvenor superstructure being
 645 relatively flexible compared with the soil- foundation stiffness.

646 The closure of the bridge span due to the nearly symmetric
 647 movements of the South and Centre Piers resulted in tunnelling-
 648 induced bending moments in the arch. Hogging moments de-

Figure 12. Comparison of tunnelling-induced deformed configurations associated with PSFE and two-stage FC elastic models (scale factor of 200)

Figure 13. Displacement vectors at top of South Pier (see survey targets in Fig. 2)

649 veloped at mid-span of the arch, where the extreme fibres at the
 650 top of the arch and deck came under tension from the bending
 651 action. As each arch rib in the bridge takes the form of a rect-
 652 angular welded box, the numerical models in FE and TSAM
 653 enable the direct calculation of the percentage utilisation of
 654 the capacity of the arches using the combined elastic axial and
 655 bending stresses induced by tunnelling. For comparison Table 3
 656 reports that the tunnelling-induced maximum stresses at the ex-
 657 treme fibres of the cross-section of the arch are systematically
 658 lower than 4.5% of the yield stress of mild steel across all inter-
 659 action models (both TSAM and FE).

660 The uncoupled greenfield analysis in which greenfield dis-
 661 placements were applied to the foundation of the frame re-
 662 sulted in the greatest structural movements and induced inter-
 663 nal forces. The resultant pier top movement was 31% greater
 664 than the measured movement in the field. The induced bend-
 665 ing moment in the arch was also over 30% greater than that
 666 from the 3DFE analysis. Nevertheless, in terms of percentage
 667 utilisation of the structural capacity, the uncoupled greenfield
 668 analysis gave a maximum elastic stress less than 5% the yield
 669 stress, compared with about 4% for the interaction models. In
 670 the following, the results are analysed in detail.

671 Of the interaction models, the 3DFE and PSFE models gave
 672 the largest settlement and horizontal movements for the base
 673 of the South Pier. Rather than due to how the structure was
 674 modelled, the large movements were primarily due to the larger
 675 greenfield displacements from PLAXIS as illustrated in Fig. 10
 676 previously, showing the importance of the geotechnical aspect
 677 of the assessment. The tilting and, as a result, the induced

Table 3. Comparison of bridge response predicted by different analysis methods

	3DFE	PSFE	FC springs	LC springs		DC springs	Greenfield uncoupled	Field measurements
				LC1	LC2			
SOUTH PIER BASE								
u (mm)	3.06	3.26	2.32	2.18	2.17	2.23	2.62	-
w (mm)	3.86	4.00	3.63	3.64	3.34	3.34	3.64	-
r_y (tilt)	-1:4068	-1:3129	-1:3375	-1:3355	-1:3044	-1:3010	-1:2656	-
SOUTH PIER TOP*								
u (mm)	7.53	8.91	7.73	7.63	8.17	8.30	9.50	7.0
w (mm)	3.86	4.00	3.63	3.64	3.34	3.34	3.64	3.3
ARCH ABOVE TUNNEL								
Max. w (mm)	-19.40	-23.94	-18.57	-18.13	-19.72	-20.12	-23.58	-
Max. M (kNm)	4212	5489	4565	4480	4762	4844	5629	-
Max. N (kN)	1059	1051	995	977	1093	1057	1228	-
Capacity utilised**	3.5%	4.5%	3.8%	3.7%	3.9%	4.0%	4.6%	-

* Taken at 2.667 m below deck level for comparing with field measurements (Fig. 2)

** Yield stress of mild steel taken as 250 MPa

bending moment from the PSFE model were notably greater (by 30%) than from the 3DFE model because the calibrated foundation length L adopted for scaling the PSFE model was optimised for the horizontal degree of freedom, with the result that foundation rotations would be over-predicted. This illustrates the shortcomings of performing a plane-strain analysis for a three-dimensional bridge and foundation system. It is critical to select the foundation length L judiciously when scaling the structure so that the key structural response, *e.g.* closing of the bridge piers and compression of the span in this case, could be captured realistically.

Considering the continuum interaction models, the footing rotation obtained from the FC elastic analysis was 20% greater than that from the 3DFE solution, while the settlement was 6% smaller. Despite the greenfield foundation displacements being greater in the PLAXIS analysis, the 3DFE analysis still predicted smaller tilting of the South Pier, and as a result, smaller induced internal forces and smaller utilisation of the structural capacity. Nevertheless, the FC solution was closer than PSFE to the 3DFE results. The salient characteristics of the deformed deformation were also in good agreement (see Fig. 12). The predicted increase of stress within the arches was very small in both cases, between 3.8% for the FC solution and 3.5% for the 3DFE model.

The different TSAM elastic models can be readily compared in Table 3, considering that the greenfield input and frame model were identical. Amongst these approaches, the FC and LC1 models gave smaller foundation rotations, pier top movements and distortion of the arches because the soil stiffness matrix did not account for foundation embedment. This resulted in more flexible foundations and, thus, reduced transmission of greenfield rotations from the soil to the piers. The DC analysis, the spring-model which is the simplest to implement (being based on empirical expressions of foundation geometry and soil Young's modulus), gave higher pier rotation and induced forces than the FC analysis, but still smaller than PSFE results. The difference between locally-coupled (LC2) and decoupled (DC) springs in movements and internal forces calculated was minor, consistent with the observation from Gazetas (1991a) that the effect of roto-translational coupling is negligible for surface

and shallow footings.

When considering the displacement vectors at the top of the South Pier (Fig. 13) and how they compared with field data, the direction and magnitude of the displacement from 3DFE and FC analyses were closest to field measurements, with the displacement exceeding the field results by only 10%. The PSFE analysis was also consistent with field measurements in terms of direction, exceeding the field magnitude by 26%. The effect of SSI was notable from the difference between interaction results and the uncoupled greenfield analysis, which deviated the greatest extent from field measurements by inducing the highest horizontal movements and rotation.

The measured pier settlement was approximately 0.9 times the average movements obtained from the SSI analyses, while the direction of the total displacement at the prism location was well captured by FC TSAM and FE analyses. The upward deflection of the deck in the span above the tunnel and the downward deflection in the adjacent spans were also well captured in the monitoring data through track trolley surveys (Wong, 2019; Faherty et al., 2022), although the volume loss could not be directly deduced from the surveys because the movements were of the ballasted tracks instead of the deck.

In conclusion, it has been demonstrated that TSAM can provide accurate and reliable assessments for relatively flexible bridges when compared with FE coupled analysis (considering steady-state tunnelling) despite the sparse available field data. Also, FE and TSAM results indicate that a flexible structure like the Grosvenor Bridge, with its internal hinges and roller-joints, would deform by following the greenfield displacements quite closely, and thus the deformed shapes from an SSI or an uncoupled greenfield analysis are not too dissimilar for relatively flexible bridges.

4.3. Applicability of linear TSAM elastic models

When adopting linear elastic TSAM, tunnelling-induced displacements and structural internal forces are directly proportional to the tunnelling volume loss (because greenfield movements scale linearly with volume loss). In reality, this linearity between structural deformations and the tunnelling volume loss may not hold above a moderate value of volume loss. In

757 this section, the applicability of the TSAM is evaluated for the
 758 Grosvenor Bridge case study above the design volume loss of
 759 1% and, then, guidance for designers is drawn.

760 First, we tested the fundamental assumption of TSAM that
 761 the tunnelling process is not affected by the structure; for this
 762 to hold, in FE analyses the extent and shape of the plastic zone
 763 around the tunnel must be limited around the tunnel periphery
 764 and not extend up to the plastic zone underneath the footings.
 765 To assess plastic zones, Fig. 14a shows yielding points predicted
 766 by PSFE interaction analyses for volume loss between
 767 1% and 3%. Results show that the plastic region arising from
 768 the tunnel excavation alone (foundation loads being ignored)
 769 are confined around the tunnel and the vertical sides of the pier
 770 foundations (where tension cut-off was reached), without bridg-
 771 ing between the two. Next, we evaluated the linearity between
 772 volume loss and bridge and soil displacements. For the FE and
 773 TSAM analyses, Fig. 14b plots the upward deck movement of
 774 the bridge span directly above the tunnel: coupled finite el-
 775 ement and two-stage modelling results are equivalent from a
 776 practical point of view with PSFE results being nearly linear
 777 and only slightly diverge from TSAM predictions above a vol-
 778 ume loss of 2%. Also, in Fig. 14c, the increase in the greenfield
 779 soil movements with volume loss obtained at the footprint of
 780 the South Pier foundation from PSFE analyses is plotted. Re-
 781 sults show that the greenfield soil movements increase almost
 782 perfectly linearly with volume loss up to about $V_L = 2\%$. The
 783 linear variations obtained confirmed the fundamental assump-
 784 tion of the corresponding TSAM analyses at the relevant range
 785 of V_L concerned.

786 Second, the mobilised shear stress underneath the founda-
 787 tion from TSAM were estimated. The theoretical basis for this
 788 are the stiffness matrix approach of the superstructure and the
 789 principle of action and reaction: the average tunnelling-induced
 790 stresses within the soil can be estimated from the tunnelling-
 791 induced forces applied by the superstructure to the foundation.
 792 The assumption that soil-foundation stresses only develop at the
 793 footing footprint is conservative, as it neglects the normal and
 794 shear stresses that could be mobilised along the vertical (lateral)
 795 surfaces of the embedded footing; the tunnelling-induced verti-
 796 cal and horizontal forces at the footings were normalised solely
 797 by the soil-footing basal contact area. Applying this approach
 798 to the linear elastic FC TSAM results, the interface shear stress
 799 for the South and Centre Piers are approximately 16 kPa for
 800 $V_L = 1\%$. This is less than 10% of the undrained shear strength
 801 of London Clay (200 kPa), which makes the adoption of linear
 802 elastic lumped foundation springs very reasonable. In fact, one
 803 may assume that the linearisation should hold as long as the
 804 mobilised strength in the springs is less than an appropriately
 805 low threshold percentage of the undrained shear strength of the
 806 soil. As the contact shear stress increases linearly with volume
 807 loss, for this case study, a linear elastic TSAM approach should
 808 therefore be valid for volume losses of up to 2–3%, as also con-
 809 firmed by deck displacement in Fig. 14b.

810 To sum up, as practical guidance, three checks are proposed
 811 to verify the applicability of linear TSAM (linearising green-
 812 field input with tunnel volume loss, assuming linear ground
 813 model and soil-foundation interfaces being perfect ties), with

Figure 14. Effect of increasing volume loss on plastic zone and linearity: (a) plastic points in PSFE analyses for varying volume losses, (b) mid-span uplift of the arch above the tunnel, and (c) greenfield soil movements at centre of South Pier foundation footprint in PSFE analyses

814 the designer selecting appropriate threshold values:

- 815 • *GF checks*: a greenfield PSFE analysis could be carried out to assess (i) that the plastic zone around the tunnel is adequately distant from the foundations and (ii) the linearity of greenfield movements at the foundation footprint; and
- 816
- 817
- 818
- 819
- 820 • *SSI check*: a SSI TSAM analysis could be carried out to evaluate that (iii) the values of the shear stresses due to tunnelling remain within an acceptable fraction of the soil shear strength (*e.g.* predicted within 10% for the Grosvenor case at the design volume loss).
- 821
- 822
- 823
- 824

825 5. Interaction results for Putney Bridge

826 This section investigates the influence of bridge stiffness by
 827 analysing the tunnelling-induced response of Putney Bridge,
 828 which is a relatively stiff structure. Two assessments of the
 829 tunnelling-induced movements were conducted using the in-
 830 house frame model on lumped springs: (i) an uncoupled green-
 831 field analysis in which greenfield movements are imposed di-
 832 rectly to the foundation nodes of the bridge and (ii) a two-
 833 stage analysis method (TSAM) incorporating fully coupled
 834 (FC) springs to represent soil-structure interaction. Fig. 15
 835 compares the results of the uncoupled greenfield analysis and
 836 TSAM considering SSI, while Table 4 shows the predicted dis-
 837 placements and rotations at key structural locations.

838 We first consider the results of the uncoupled greenfield analysis. In this case, the displacements were applied directly at the foundation level, and the rotations of the foundations were assumed to match the gradient of the greenfield settlement trough. In Fig. 15, this causes Piers 2 and 3 to rotate inward towards the tunnel axis and, in turn, this induces the downward deflection of the central span. This deformation pattern differs from the one observed previously for the Grosvenor Bridge where the central span deflects upwards as a result of the hinged pier-to-arch connection. As a result, the uncoupled greenfield analysis predicts significant bending-related stresses in the piers, arches and deck.

850 From the SSI results, shown by the deformed shape in
 851 Fig. 15, the stiffness of the arches and deck prevents the full
 852 “greenfield” inward horizontal movements of the top parts of
 853 the piers as well as the pier rotation. The resulting pier dis-
 854 placements are predominantly vertical, with magnitudes of ap-
 855 proximately 90% of the greenfield settlement. This leads to
 856 smaller bending and deflection of the decks and arches in the
 857 interaction analysis than in the uncoupled greenfield analysis
 858 (see Table 4). A closer inspection of the results shows that,
 859 due to the high stiffness of the superstructure, the foundations
 860 are displaced slightly outward (horizontally) from the tunnel in
 861 the interaction model, opposite to the direction of the greenfield
 862 movements, which would be inwards.

863 TSAM results indicated that the foundation movement dis-
 864 tribution can change qualitatively due to a relatively stiff arch
 865 bridge; a deformation assessment of such a structure using
 866 greenfield movements (with or without a modification factor) is

Figure 15. Deformed shape of Putney Bridge from different analysis methods (scale factor of 1000)

867 not recommended. For reference, the second moment of area
 868 of the arches of Putney Bridge is three orders of magnitude
 869 greater than that of the relatively flexible Grosvenor Bridge,
 870 while the spring stiffness for the Putney foundations is neces-
 871 sarily smaller as the its pier footprint is only about half the size
 872 of that of the Grosvenor Bridge. Furthermore, the induced gra-
 873 dient in the central span when considering SSI is only a fraction
 874 of the value from the uncoupled greenfield analysis; therefore, a
 875 serviceability assessment which informs decisions on strength-
 876 ening works for utilities could potentially be misled by not con-
 877 sidering SSI in a such a stiff structure.

Table 4. Response of Putney Bridge to tunnel excavation

	FC springs	Greenfield uncoupled
PIER 2 BASE		
u (mm)	-0.09	1.58
w (mm)	2.18	2.46
r_y (tilt)	-1:78471	-1:2304
PIER 3 BASE		
u (mm)	0.02	-1.58
w (mm)	2.19	2.46
r_y (tilt)	1:77615	1:2304
MID-SPAN ABOVE TUNNEL		
w (mm)	2.31	4.33
Max. deck gradient	1:130775	1:7591
Max. arch bending (kNm)	2009	23903
SPRINGERS OF ARCH		
Max. arch bending (kNm)	16906	49664

878 **6. 3D TSAM analysis of Grosvenor Bridge during tunnel**
879 **advancement**

880 TSAM enables the direct analysis of the bridge response as
881 the tunnel excavation progresses beneath the structure, in tran-
882 sient stages, allowing the study of both the spatial and tempo-
883 ral aspects of induced displacements. Transient deformations
884 sometimes cause greater distortions than steady-state displacements.
885 It is of interest to study this transient response of bridges
886 to tunnelling.

887 For transient analyses, a 3D bridge model and the estimate of
888 a transient input greenfield displacement field (*e.g.* from empir-
889 ical methods) are required. Lumped foundation springs based
890 on the half-space theory are intrinsically 3D in nature, having
891 local stiffness and interaction terms for all six degrees of free-
892 dom (*i.e.* three translations and three rotations); therefore, tran-
893 sient TSAM analyses can readily study the roto-translational
894 response of the bridge in the transverse and longitudinal direc-
895 tions, as well as the torsional foundation response about the
896 vertical axes of piers.

897 In this section, a transient analysis of the Grosvenor Bridge is
898 presented as an example of this TSAM application. The actual
899 bridge superstructure consists of 10 individual bridge frames,
900 each of which was modelled as plane frames composed of 2D
901 beam elements with suitable connections. These frames were
902 connected to 3D beam elements representing the bridge piers.
903 At each pier base, fully coupled (FC) roto-translational springs
904 were introduced at each master-node of the footings. A green-
905 field displacement field evolving with time was applied, cor-
906 responding to different TBM positions; settlements and hori-
907 zontal movements were estimated by combining steady-state
908 transverse displacements by Wong et al. (2025) with cumula-
909 tive distribution function profiles in the longitudinal direction
910 (Camós and Molins, 2015). The greenfield set of forces (\mathbf{p}_{gf})
911 was applied to the foundation master-nodes at each stage, and
912 the structural response then computed using TSAM; consider-
913 ing the linear elastic TSAM model, all stages are independently
914 analysed.

915 Fig. 16 illustrates the differential horizontal displacements of
916 pier heads at the front and rear edges of the piers and the
917 rotation of the piers about the vertical axis as a result of the TBM
918 approach. Due to asymmetric loading and differential pier set-
919 tlements between the front and rear sides of the bridge, each
920 pier is subjected to a small but not insignificant twisting ac-
921 tion. This 3D rotational response causes a differential hori-
922 zontal movement between the front and rear edges of the pier
923 heads, which is also confirmed by field data as follows.

924 Fig. 17a and 17d presents the settlement of the South and
925 Centre Piers respectively during the TBM approach. From the
926 FC analysis, the front edge of the piers begins to settle im-
927 mediately before the approach of the TBM from the downstream
928 side (+ve y direction). This movement causes the rear edge
929 of the piers to lift up momentarily, given that each pier is
930 relatively rigid. The entire South bridge pier settles by about
931 4 mm after the TBM completely goes past the 60 m long
932 bridge pier. As discussed above for the 2D steady-state mod-
933 elling, the flexible nature of the bridge frames results in the
934 pier settlements being

Figure 16. 3D model of Grosvenor Bridge for TSAM

934 almost identical to the greenfield settlement values. Settlement
935 monitoring data from the survey prisms also confirm the earlier
936 onset of settlement at the front edge relative to the rear edge
937 and the initial uplift of the rear edge. The SSI analysis was able
938 to predict the transient, out-of-plane tilting of the bridge in
939 the longitudinal direction of the tunnel drive.

940 Fig. 17b and 17e presents the predicted and measured hori-
941 zontal displacements of the pier heads. The front edge began
942 to deflect horizontally earlier and faster than the rear. The final
943 horizontal displacements of the South and Centre Piers were up
944 to about 8 mm and 6 mm respectively, indicating the closing of
945 the pier heads either side of the tunnel due to in-plane tilting
946 of the piers in the direction transverse to the tunnel drive. The
947 SSI results suggest up to 2.2 mm of differential movement be-
948 tween the front and rear edges. The results show good agree-
949 ment with field data. The SSI model is able to reproduce the
950 transient twisting of the bridge piers as evidenced by the differ-
951 ential horizontal movements. This effect would be underestimated
952 if the interaction between translational and rotational degrees
953 of freedom is ignored (*e.g.* with decoupled springs). The results
954 for uncoupled greenfield results are also shown, indicating that
955 the in-plane stiffness of the bridge structure reduces the calcu-
956 lated horizontal displacements of the piers.

957 Finally, the predicted and measured out-of-plane horizontal
958 displacement of the bridge piers are shown in Fig. 17c and
959 17f. The predicted displacements for both the South and Centre
960 Piers are very small, with a maximum of about 1.2 mm. Al-
961 though consistent with the out-of-plane tilting of the piers and
962 the differential settlement between the front and the rear of the
963 piers shown in subfigures (a) and (b), they are not fully con-
964 sistent with the measured values, which appeared slightly erratic.

965 This transient 3D TSAM analysis underscores the impor-
966 tance of modelling both horizontal and rotational SSI effects,
967 especially for bridges with spatial continuity and stiffness. Cou-
968 pled spring models are capable of capturing 3D deformation
969 mechanisms that simpler approaches are not able to reproduce.
970 These include rotational distortions about the vertical axis and
971 the resulting torsional stresses on the superstructure.

972 Overall, the results demonstrate that TSAM, when extended

(a)

(d)

(b)

(e)

(c)

(f)

Figure 17. South Pier head (a) settlement, (b) in-plane horizontal displacement and (c) out-of-plane horizontal displacement; Centre Pier head (d) settlement, (e) in-plane horizontal displacement and (f) out-of-plane horizontal displacement

973 to 3D and transient conditions, offers a powerful and efficient 1028
 974 framework for evaluating the evolving response of bridges dur- 1029
 975 ing TBM advancement. Such analyses are valuable for both 1030
 976 design and construction monitoring, as they inform the inter- 1031
 977 pretation of real-time data and help identify intermediate stages 1032
 978 of increased vulnerability that may be lost in a steady-state anal- 1033
 979 ysis. 1034

980 **7. Guideline for future risk assessments of bridges on shal-**
 981 **low foundations**

982 TSAM has the advantage of enabling quick sensitivity stud- 1039
 983 ies of the greenfield displacement field, structural configura- 1040
 984 tions (and nonlinearities) and the resulting SSI that can mod- 1041
 985 ify the foundation movement distribution. In addition to this 1042
 986 versatility and the possibility to perform either steady-state or 1043
 987 transient analysis of plane-frame or three-dimensional bridges, 1044
 988 the comparison with coupled finite element analysis has demon-
 989 strated a similar predictive capability of TSAM with its intrin-
 990 sic 3D nature which bypasses the approximations required by
 991 equivalent plane-strain models. Therefore, TSAM is always
 992 recommended in place of uncoupled greenfield analysis (im-
 993 posing greenfield displacements directly to foundations).

994 At the preliminary phases of an assessment, due to the lack
 995 of a generalised method to estimate relative bridge-foundation-
 996 soil stiffness, interaction models are almost always needed for
 997 bridge assessment in the presence of tunnelling, as opposed
 998 to building assessments for which recognised empirical ap-
 999 proaches are available. On the one hand, for relatively stiff
 1000 bridges, interaction models able to account for SSI effects on
 1001 foundation movements are necessary. Even for relatively flexi-
 1002 ble bridges (*e.g.* Grosvenor Bridge) which conform closely to
 1003 greenfield movements, it is difficult to assess whether SSI is
 1004 negligible *a priori*. In this context, TSAM is a suitable tool to
 1005 assess the relevance of SSI, and decide how to proceed further
 1006 in the design process.

1007 Regarding the complexity of the lumped-spring models for
 1008 the foundation, even the simplest interaction method with Win-
 1009 kler decoupled (DC) springs can produce realistic results of
 1010 structural movements and internal forces. Such decoupled
 1011 springs can be readily implemented in most commercial struc-
 1012 tural computer programs for a TSAM. Uncertainties regard-
 1013 ing Winkler spring constants can be addressed by a sensitiv-
 1014 ity study, considering available analytical and empirical expres-
 1015 sions to account for embedment, shape, as well as the bedrock
 1016 depth-to-footing width (*e.g.* Gazetas, 1991a; Pais and Kausel,
 1017 1988). Therefore, TSAM based on Winkler ground models is
 1018 suggested, as a first step, to assess the level of relative soil-
 1019 structure stiffness and the expected deformation mechanism of
 1020 the bridge, which is relevant to the design of monitoring work
 1021 and the expected serviceability/ultimate states to be analysed in
 1022 detail.

1023 The observation that the steel Grosvenor bridge was rela-
 1024 tively flexible with respect to the underlying stiff soil should
 1025 not be extrapolated or generalised to all steel arch bridges. All
 1026 the interaction analyses in this study incorporated roller con-
 1027 nections (between deck and piers) as well as frictionless hinges

(between arches and piers) that reduced the superstructure reac-
 tion forces acting on the piers. Wong (2019) demonstrated that
 the bridge response to tunnelling would become significantly
 stiffer if the internal hinges were removed and, thus, SSI is sen-
 sitive to the degree of fixity of internal connections in steel arch
 frames. Structural details and internal connections can be read-
 ily included in TSAM.

The final recommendation is to evaluate if the interaction
 problem can be considered in an elastic regime; for this, we
 have suggested: (i) estimating the extent of the plastic zone
 and the linearity of the greenfield soil movements with V_L (us-
 ing a greenfield finite-element analysis of tunnelling), along
 with (ii) an assessment of tunnelling-induced mobilised shear
 strength at the foundation (using TSAM).

Fig. 18 summarises the geotechnical and structural design
 processes, including TSAM applicability checks, in a flow
 chart.

Figure 18. Process of tunnelling impact assessment for bridges on shallow foundations

1045 8. Conclusions

1046 This paper presents a methodology for analysing the interac-
1047 tion between a bored tunnel and an existing bridge on shallow
1048 foundations: the two-stage analysis method (TSAM), which de-
1049 couples the geotechnical and structural aspects of the problem
1050 but retains their interaction through spring-based foundations.
1051 First, this work builds on insights from the Thames Tideway
1052 Tunnel project and examines the Grosvenor Bridge and Putney
1053 Bridge as case studies. The predictions of two-stage modelling
1054 for varying levels of complexity (fully coupled, locally cou-
1055 pled, and decoupled springs) were benchmarked against field
1056 data and more rigorous coupled plane-strain (PSFE) and three-
1057 dimensional finite element (3DFE) models. Results illustrate
1058 how structural stiffness, soil response, and interaction mod-
1059 elling assumptions influence the prediction of bridge displac-
1060 ements during tunnelling. The main conclusions are given be-
1061 low.

- 1062 • The TSAM framework offers a practical balance between
1063 simplicity and accuracy, making it suitable for preliminary
1064 assessments of tunnelling impacts on existing bridges. A
1065 comparison of TSAM and FE models demonstrates that
1066 spring-based two-stage method can provide results that are
1067 consistent with those of more advanced coupled FE anal-
1068 ysis, capturing essential aspects of the structural and SSI
1069 behaviours, with minimal requirements for calibration of
1070 the spring constants, given readily available expressions
1071 from the half-space theory. Also, TSAM can be extended
1072 to capture 3D effects during tunnel advancement, avoiding
1073 the computational demands of 3D FE analysis or the ap-
1074 proximations required by equivalent plane-strain FE mod-
1075 els. TSAM results closely matched monitoring data in
1076 both steady-state and transient conditions in the Grosvenor
1077 case study.
- 1078 • Results have confirmed the need to move beyond green-
1079 field assumptions and account for interaction effects, es-
1080 pecially when dealing with stiff bridge structures. For
1081 relatively flexible bridges, such as the Grosvenor Bridge,
1082 the interaction response closely follows greenfield pat-
1083 terns due to the limited structural restraint and internal
1084 articulation. In such cases, uncoupled greenfield analy-
1085 ses may yield similar deformed shapes to coupled mod-
1086 els, although TSAM still provides a better estimate of in-
1087 ternal forces and mobilised capacities. For relatively stiff
1088 bridges, such as the Putney Bridge, greenfield assumptions
1089 significantly over-predict internal actions and misrepresent
1090 the deformation mechanism. TSAM results have showed
1091 that SSI can change both the magnitude and direction of
1092 pier movements. This has implications for serviceability,
1093 crack control, and condition monitoring strategy.
- 1094 • Even simplified TSAMs using decoupled (Winkler)
1095 springs, such as those formulated by Gazetas (1991a), lead
1096 to realistic predictions of structural displacements and in-
1097 ternal forces, making them suitable for preliminary assess-
1098 ments. These models are easy to implement in commercial

software and produce adequate first estimates of the effects
of SSI.

- The applicability of linear TSAM must be checked by
evaluating plasticity and mobilised shear strength beneath
foundations. For the Grosvenor Bridge case, estimates
based on TSAM and PSFE indicated that the elastic range
remains valid for tunnel volume losses up to 2–3%, which
is more than adequate for typical urban tunnelling projects
in stiff clays. Practical checks combining a greenfield FE
analysis and the comparison of shear strength with esti-
mates from TSAM were recommended.
- The equivalence between plane-strain and three-
dimensional coupled finite element models for steady-state
assessment was investigated, and a calibration procedure
for defining the equivalent foundation width in plane-
strain analysis was proposed. As perfect equivalence
is not achievable, we suggested that the foundation
width should be selected based on the dominant mode
of structural response, using engineering judgement.
For the Grosvenor Bridge case study, the foundation
width was calibrated to match horizontal stiffness, at the
cost of over-estimating the rotational movements. This
likely explains the higher internal forces and movements
predicted by the plane-strain FE model compared to the
three-dimensional FE analysis.

TSAM offers a reliable and efficient framework for evaluat-
ing tunnel-soil-bridge interactions. It enables sensitivity stud-
ies on greenfield displacement fields, foundation stiffness, and
superstructure configurations, and it supports both steady-state
and transient assessments. It is suggested as a pathway from
greenfield displacement estimation to integrated structural anal-
ysis, providing a useful tool for geotechnical and structural de-
signers to make rational risk assessments and plan monitoring
works.

Future work in this field could extend TSAM frameworks to
incorporate nonlinear bridge behaviour and probabilistic input
parameters for risk-informed assessment to cover the uncertain-
ties in the superstructure and geotechnical domains.

1137 Acknowledgements

1138 The first author's postgraduate studies forming the basis of this
1139 paper was partially supported by the Geotechnical Engineering
1140 Office, Civil Engineering and Development Department of the
1141 Hong Kong S.A.R. Government and the Hong Kong Institution
1142 of Engineers Arthur & Louise May Memorial Scholarship.

1143 The authors would like to acknowledge Ferrovia Agroman
1144 and Laing O'Rourke JV for providing them with access to the
1145 monitoring data.

1146 CRediT author statement

1147 **E.K.L. Wong:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software,
1148 Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writ-
1149 ing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Visualiza-
1150 tion. **A. Franza:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software,

1151 Validation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Edit- 1178
 1152 ing, Supervision. **P. Hewitt**: Investigation, Resources, Data
 1153 Curation. **G.M.B. Viggiani**: Conceptualization, Methodology,
 1154 Resources, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Project
 1155 administration.

1156 Appendix A: Formulation of soil stiffness matrix for fully- 1157 coupled (FC) springs solution

1158 This appendix describes the procedure followed in assem- 1180
 1159 bling the soil stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_{soil} . Elastic solutions such as 1181
 1160 Love (1927) and Cheung and Nag (1968) give the displacements 1182
 1161 in a homogeneous elastic half-space under the applica- 1183
 1162 tion of forces on the surface. The solutions are of the form

$$\mathbf{F}\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{u} \quad (16)$$

1163 where \mathbf{F} is the soil flexibility matrix, \mathbf{q} is the vector of applied 1185
 1164 vertical and horizontal forces and \mathbf{u} is the vector of horizontal 1186
 1165 and vertical displacements on the surface of the half-space. 1187

1166 Love (1927) gives the displacements at a point (x, y) on the 1188
 1167 surface of the half-space under a concentrated horizontal force 1188
 1168 H_0 as

$$u_x = \frac{H_0}{2\pi G} \left(\frac{1-\nu}{r} + \nu \frac{x^2}{r^3} \right) \quad (17a)$$

$$u_y = \frac{\nu H_0}{2\pi G} \left(\frac{xy}{r^3} \right) \quad (17b)$$

$$u_z = \frac{(1-2\nu)H_0}{4\pi G} \left(\frac{x}{r^2} \right) \quad (17c)$$

and the displacements under a concentrated vertical force V_0 as

$$u_x = -(1-2\nu) \frac{V_0}{4\pi G} \frac{x}{r^2} \quad (18a)$$

$$u_y = -(1-2\nu) \frac{V_0}{4\pi G} \frac{y}{r^2} \quad (18b)$$

$$u_z = \frac{(1-\nu)V_0}{2\pi G r} \quad (18c)$$

1169 where r is the plan distance between the point of force applica-
 1170 tion and the point at which displacements are evaluated
 1171 (Fig. 19a). The expressions in Eq. (17a) to (18c) are used to
 1172 obtain the off-diagonal terms of the soil flexibility matrix \mathbf{F} but
 1173 are undefined at the point of force application ($r = 0$).

1174 The diagonal terms of \mathbf{F} may be determined by integrating
 1175 the forces over a rectangular area and evaluating the total dis-
 1176 placements accordingly. Cheung and Nag (1968) give the dis-
 1177 placements beneath a rectangular area of dimensions $a \times b$ under

applied horizontal and vertical forces H_0 and V_0 as

$$u_x = \frac{2H_0(1-\nu^2)}{a\pi E} \left[C \sinh^{-1} \frac{1}{C} + \sinh^{-1} C \right] + \frac{2H_0\nu(1+\nu)}{a\pi E} (\sinh^{-1} C) \quad (19a)$$

$$u_z = \frac{2V_0(1-\nu^2)}{a\pi E} \left[C \sinh^{-1} \frac{1}{C} + \sinh^{-1} C \right] \quad (19b)$$

1179 where $C = a/b$ and E is the Young's modulus of the elastic
 1180 half-space (Fig. 19b). This gives the diagonal terms and com-
 1181 pletes \mathbf{F} .

1182 The soil stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_s is therefore given by the inverse
 1183 of the soil flexibility matrix:

$$\mathbf{K}_s = \mathbf{F}^{-1} \quad (20)$$

1184 For a structure consisting of multiple individual footings
 1185 which are discretised into an array of n nodes, following the
 1186 procedure outlined above generates a $3n \times 3n$ soil stiffness ma-
 1187 trix \mathbf{K}_s . This enables the coupling between different footings
 1188 across the surface of the soil.

(a)

(b)

Figure 19. Displacements on surface of homogeneous elastic half-space: (a) displacements at locations other than point of force application and (b) displacements at point of force application

1189 **Appendix B: Formulation of soil stiffness matrix for decoupled (DC) or locally-coupled (LC2) springs solution** 1212

1190
1191 This appendix describes the formulation of static foundation spring constants following Gazetas (1991a) and Gazetas (1991b). For a rigid footing on the surface of an infinite elastic half-space, the relevant spring constants for the three relevant degrees of freedom for a 2D problem is given by Eq. (i)–(iii) in Table 5. The springs are functions of the plan geometry of the footing and soil properties.

Table 5. Static spring stiffness for rigid foundation on surface of elastic continuum Gazetas (1991a) and Gazetas (1991b)

Mode	Stiffness (Load per unit displacement)	Depth of zone of influence
$H \rightarrow \infty$		
Vertical (z)	$K_z = [GL/(1-\nu)](0.73 + 1.5\chi^{0.75})$ with $\chi = A/(2L)^2$	(i) 2.5–7.5 B
Horizontal (x)	$K_x = [GL/(2-\nu)](2 + 2.5\chi^{0.85})$	(ii) 1–3 B
Rotational (about y)	$K_{ry} = [G/(1-\nu)]I_y^{0.75}(L/B)^{0.25}(2.4 + 0.5B/L)$	(iii) B
$H \neq \infty$		
Vertical (z)	$K_z = \frac{GL}{B/H} [0.73 + 1.54(\frac{B}{L})^{0.75}] (1 + \frac{1}{1+2B/L})$	(iv)

See Fig. 20 for notations.

Figure 20. Foundation on surface of elastic continuum

1198 The presence of a rigid boundary affects the spring stiffness in different ways for different modes of movement. The effect of the rigid boundary may be assessed by considering the zone of influence. Gazetas (1991b) gives the approximate range of zone of influence for different modes of movements. For example, for a vertical applied load, the zone of influence ranges from 2.5B for a rectangular footing to 7.5B for a strip footing. It is notable that the effect of a rigid boundary has the greatest effect on the vertical stiffness. It increases the vertical stiffness by a factor of $(1 + \frac{B/H}{1+2B/L})$. For horizontal and rotational movements, the effect of the rigid bottom boundary may reasonably be ignored if the depth of the rigid boundary is greater than the zone of influence. The foundation stiffness matrix is therefore written as:

$$\mathbf{K}_f = \begin{bmatrix} K_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{ry} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

1213 The spring stiffnesses for a footing embedded in an infinite elastic half-space are given by Eq. (v)–(vii) in Table 6. Embedment substantially increases the spring constants compared with the case without embedment, in particular the rotational stiffness.

1214 Gazetas (1991a) also gives an additional term for the coupling between translation and rotation for an embedded footing. Hence the foundation stiffness matrix for an embedded footing is written as:

$$\mathbf{K}_f = \begin{bmatrix} K_{x,emb} & 0 & \frac{1}{3}K_{x,emb}d \\ 0 & K_{z,emb} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{3}K_{x,emb}d & 0 & K_{ry,emb} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

Table 6. Static spring stiffness for rigid foundation embedded in elastic continuum after Gazetas (1991a)

Mode	Stiffness (Load per unit displacement)
Vertical (z)	$K_{z,emb} = K_z[1 + (2/21)(D/B)(1 + 1.3\chi)] [1 + 0.2(A_w/A)^{2/3}]$ (v)
Horizontal (x)	$K_{x,emb} = K_x[1 + 0.21(D/B)^{0.5}] [1 + 0.69[(h/B)(A_w/L^2)]^{0.4}]$ (vi)
Rotational (about y)	$K_{ry,emb} = K_{ry}\{1 + 2.52(d/B) [1 + (2d/B)(d/D)^{-0.2}(B/L)^{0.5}]\}$ (vii)

See Fig. 21 for notations.

Figure 21. Foundation embedded in elastic continuum

1221 **References**

1222 Bentley, 2020a. Material Models - PLAXIS 2D CONNECT Edition V20.
 1223 PLAXIS manuals , 218–221.

1224 Bentley, 2020b. Reference Manual - PLAXIS 2D CONNECT Edition V20.
 1225 PLAXIS manuals , 250–251.

1226 Boldini, D., Losacco, N., Franza, A., DeJong, M.J., Xu, J., Marshall, A.M.,
 1227 2021. Tunneling-Induced Deformation of Bare Frame Structures on Sand:
 1228 Numerical Study of Building Deformations. *Journal of Geotechnical and*
 1229 *Geoenvironmental Engineering* 147, 04021116. doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.
 1230 1943-5606.0002627.

1231 Callisto, L., Rampello, S., Viggiani, G.M.B., 2013. Soil–structure interaction
 1232 for the seismic design of the Messina Strait Bridge. *Soil Dynamics and*
 1233 *Earthquake Engineering* 52, 103–115. doi:10.1016/j.soildyn.2013.
 1234 05.005.

1235 Camós, C., Molins, C., 2015. 3D analytical prediction of building damage due
 1236 to ground subsidence produced by tunnelling. *Tunnelling and Underground*
 1237 *Space Technology* 50, 424–437. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2015.08.012.

1238 Cheng, C.Y., Dasari, G.R., Chow, Y.K., Leung, C.F., 2007. Finite element
 1239 analysis of tunnel–soil–pile interaction using displacement controlled
 1240 model. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology* 22, 450–466.
 1241 doi:10.1016/j.tust.2006.08.002.

1242 Cheung, Y.K., Nag, D.K., 1968. Plates and Beams on Elastic Foundations
 1243 –Linear and Non-Linear Behaviour. *Géotechnique* 18, 250–260.
 1244 doi:10.1680/geot.1968.18.2.250.

1245 Crossrail, 2008. Ground Settlement. Crossrail Information Paper
 1246 D12. URL: [https://learninglegacy.crossrail.co.uk/
 1247 wp-content/uploads/2023/03/d12groundsettlement.pdf](https://learninglegacy.crossrail.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/d12groundsettlement.pdf).

1248 Dempsey, J.P., Li, H., 1989. A rigid rectangular footing on an elastic layer.
 1249 *Géotechnique* 39, 147–152. doi:10.1680/geot.1989.39.1.147.

1250 Dimmock, P.S., Mair, R.J., 2008. Effect of building stiffness on tunnelling-
 1251 induced ground movement. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*
 1252 23, 438–450. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2007.08.001.

1253 Faherty, R., Acikgoz, S., Wong, E.K.L., Hewitt, P., Viggiani, G.M.B., 2022.
 1254 Tunnel-soil-structure interaction mechanisms in a metallic arch bridge. *Tun-*
 1255 *nelling and Underground Space Technology* 123, 104429. doi:10.1016/j.
 1256 tust.2022.104429.

1257 Farrell, R., Mair, R., Sciotti, A., Pigorini, A., 2014. Building response to
 1258 tunnelling. *Soils and Foundations* 54, 269–279. doi:10.1016/j.sandf.
 1259 2014.04.003.

1260 Federal Highway Administration, 1985. Tolerable movement criteria for high-
 1261 way bridges. Technical Report FHWA/RD-85/107.

1262 Fox, C.D., 1868. On the widening of the Victoria Bridge and approaches to the
 1263 Victoria Station, and on new railways at Battersea. Minutes of the Proceed-
 1264 ings of the Institution of Civil Engineers 27, 68–81. doi:10.1680/imotp.
 1265 1868.23118.

1266 Franza, A., DeJong, M.J., 2019. Elastoplastic Solutions to Predict Tunneling-
 1267 Induced Load Redistribution and Deformation of Surface Structures. *Journal*
 1268 *of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering* 145, 04019007.
 1269 doi:10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0002021.

1270 Franzius, J.N., Potts, D.M., Burland, J.B., 2006. The response of surface structures
 1271 to tunnel construction. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers
 1272 - Geotechnical Engineering 159, 3–17. doi:10.1680/geng.2006.159.1.
 1273 3.

1274 Friedman, Z., Kosmatka, J.B., 1993. An improved two-node Timoshenko
 1275 beam finite element. *Computers & Structures* 47, 473–481. doi:10.1016/
 1276 0045-7949(93)90243-7.

1277 Gazetas, G., 1991a. Formulas and Charts for Impedances of Surface and Em-
 1278 bedded Foundations. *Journal of Geotechnical Engineering* 117, 1363–1381.
 1279 doi:10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9410(1991)117:9(1363).

1280 Gazetas, G., 1991b. Foundation Vibrations, in: Fang, H.Y. (Ed.), *Foundation*
 1281 *Engineering Handbook*. Springer US, Boston, MA, pp. 553–593.

1282 Giardina, G., DeJong, M.J., Mair, R.J., 2015. Interaction between surface structures
 1283 and tunnelling in sand: Centrifuge and computational modelling. *Tun-*
 1284 *nelling and Underground Space Technology* 50, 465–478. doi:10.1016/j.
 1285 tust.2015.07.016.

1286 Haji, T.K., Marshall, A.M., Franza, A., 2018. Mixed empirical-numerical
 1287 method for investigating tunnelling effects on structures. *Tunnelling and*
 1288 *Underground Space Technology* 73, 92–104. doi:10.1016/j.tust.2017.
 1289 12.008.

1290 Kerensky, O.A., Partridge, F.A., 1967. The reconstruction of the Grosvenor
 1291 Railway Bridge. Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers 36, 721–
 1292 768. doi:10.1680/iicep.1967.8471.

1293 Kerensky, O.A., Shirley, W.J., Goodearl, K.A., Harper, W.J., Selviah, R.B.,
 1294 Wood, G.K., Holloway, B.G.R., Partridge, F.A., Chapman, J.C., Upstone,
 1295 T.J., Ellis, L.G., Sowden, A.M., Turner, R.W., Cantrell, A.H., Wakeling,
 1296 T.R., 1967. The reconstruction of the Grosvenor Railway Bridge. Pro-
 1297 ceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers 38, 737–760. doi:10.1680/
 1298 iicep.1967.8195.

1299 Klar, A., Vorster, T.E.B., Soga, K., Mair, R.J., 2005. Soil-pipe interaction due
 1300 to tunnelling: comparison between Winkler and elastic continuum solutions.
 1301 *Géotechnique* 55, 461–466. doi:10.1680/geot.2005.55.6.461.

1302 Li, J., Berger, E.J., 2001. A Boussinesq–Cerruti Solution Set for Constant
 1303 and Linear Distribution of Normal and Tangential Load over a Triangular
 1304 Area. *Journal of elasticity and the physical science of solids* 63, 137–151.
 1305 doi:10.1023/A:1014013425423.

1306 Litewka, P., Rakowski, J., 1997. An Efficient Curved Beam Finite
 1307 Element. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineer-*
 1308 *ing* 40, 2629–2652. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-0207(19970730)40:
 1309 14<2629::AID-NME179>3.0.CO;2-Y.

1310 Love, A.E.H., 1927. *A Treatise on the Mathematical Theory of Elasticity*. 4th
 1311 ed., Cambridge University Press.

1312 Mair, R.J., Taylor, R.N., 1997. Bored tunnelling in the urban environment,
 1313 in: Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and
 1314 Foundation Engineering, Hamburg. pp. 2353–2385.

1315 Mair, R.J., Taylor, R.N., Bracegirdle, A., 1993. Subsurface settlement profiles
 1316 above tunnels in clays. *Géotechnique* 43, 315–320. doi:10.1680/geot.
 1317 1993.43.2.315.

1318 Mair, R.J., Taylor, R.N., Burland, J.B., 1996. Prediction of ground movements
 1319 and assessment of risk of building damage due to bored tunnelling, in: Pro-
 1320 ceedings of the International Conference on Geotechnical Aspects of an Un-
 1321 derground Construction in Soft Ground, London. pp. 713–718.

1322 Pais, A., Kausel, E., 1988. Approximate formulas for dynamic stiffnesses of
 1323 rigid foundations. *Soil Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering* 7, 213–227.
 1324 doi:10.1016/S0267-7261(88)80005-8.

1325 Peck, R.B., 1969. Deep excavations and tunneling in soft ground, in: State of
 1326 the Art Volume of the 7th International Conference on Soil Mechanics and
 1327 Foundation Engineering, Mexico. pp. 225–258.

1328 Rampello, S., Callisto, L., Viggiani, G., 2014. Predicting the seismic behaviour
 1329 of the foundations of the Messina Strait Bridge. *Bulletin of Earthquake*
 1330 *Engineering* 12, 1201–1219. doi:10.1007/s10518-013-9536-2.

1331 Rampello, S., Callisto, L., Viggiani, G.M.B., Soccodato, F.M., 2012. Evaluat-
 1332 ing the effects of tunnelling on historical buildings: The example of a new
 1333 subway in Rome. *Geomechanics and Tunnelling* 5, 275–299.

1334 Schoor, J., Wade, R., Yin, K., Stephenson, V., 2021. Assessing the impacts of
 1335 construction-induced ground movement on framed buildings. CIRIA C796,
 1336 CIRIA, London.

1337 Skempton, A.W., Henkel, D.J., 1957. Tests on London Clay from Deep Bor-
 1338 ings at Paddington, Victoria and the South Bank, in: Proceedings of the 4th
 1339 International Conference on Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering,
 1340 London. pp. 100–106.

1341 Thames Water Utilities Limited, 2012. Thames Tunnel Detailed Bridge
 1342 Assessments - Putney Road Bridge. Technical Report No. 9.15.11.
 1343 URL: [https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.
 1344 gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/
 1345 WW010001-003345-9.15.11_Putney_Road_Bridge.pdf](https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003345-9.15.11_Putney_Road_Bridge.pdf).

1346 Thames Water Utilities Limited, 2013a. Ground Investigation Report on
 1347 Route Geology. Technical Report No. 9.18 (Part 2 of 2). URL: [https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/
 1348 ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003503-9.18_
 1349 Ground_Investigation_Report_on_Route_Geology_Part2.pdf](https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003503-9.18_Ground_Investigation_Report_on_Route_Geology_Part2.pdf).

1350 Thames Water Utilities Limited, 2013b. Thames Tunnel Detailed
 1351 Bridge Assessments - Blackfriars Rail Bridge. Technical Report No.
 1352 9.15.25. URL: [https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.
 1353 gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/
 1354 WW010001-003356-9.15.25_Tunnel_and_Bridge_Assessments_
 1355 Blackfriars_Rail_Bridge.pdf](https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003356-9.15.25_Tunnel_and_Bridge_Assessments_Blackfriars_Rail_Bridge.pdf).

1356 Thames Water Utilities Limited, 2013c. Thames Tunnel Detailed
 1357 Bridge Assessments - Chelsea River Bridge. Technical Report No.
 1358 9.15.22. URL: [https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.
 1359 gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/
 1360 WW010001-003354-9.15.22_Tunnel_and_Bridge_Assessments_
 1361 Chelsea_River_Bridge.pdf](https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003354-9.15.22_Tunnel_and_Bridge_Assessments_Chelsea_River_Bridge.pdf).

1362 Thames Water Utilities Limited, 2013d. Tunnel and Bridge Assess-
 1363 ments - Assessment of the Effects of Tunnel Induced Settlement On
 1364 Blackfriars Bridge. Technical Report No. 9.15.48. URL: [https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/
 1365 ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003479-9.15.48_
 1366 Tunnel_and_Bridge_Assessments_Blackfriars_Bridge_\(A201\)
 1367 _Structure_No_33_T01_\(BR016\).pdf](https://infrastructure.planninginspectorate.gov.uk/wp-content/ipc/uploads/projects/WW010001/WW010001-003479-9.15.48_Tunnel_and_Bridge_Assessments_Blackfriars_Bridge_(A201)_Structure_No_33_T01_(BR016).pdf).

1368 Viggiani, C., 1999. Fondazioni. Hevelius Edizioni.

1369 Wilson, W., 1868. Description of the Victoria Bridge, on the line of the Victoria
 1370 Station and Pimlico Railway. Minutes of the Proceedings of the Institution
 1371 of Civil Engineers 27, 55–67. doi:10.1680/imotp.1868.23117.

1372 Withers, A.D., Page, D.P., Linney, L.F., 2001. Geology and geotechnical prop-
 1373 erties, in: Burland, J.B., Standing, J.R., Jardine, F.M. (Eds.), *Building Re-*
 1374 *sponse to tunnelling - Case studies from construction of the Jubilee Line*
 1375 *Extension, London*. Thomas Telford Publishing. volume 1, pp. 57–82.

- 1378 Wong, E.K.L., 2019. Interaction between tunnel construction and ex-
1379 isting infrastructure – numerical modelling and field observations.
1380 MPhil Thesis. Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge.
1381 URL: [https://www-geo.eng.cam.ac.uk/pdfs/abstracts/mphils/
1382 m91-wong-e-k-l-abstract.pdf](https://www-geo.eng.cam.ac.uk/pdfs/abstracts/mphils/m91-wong-e-k-l-abstract.pdf).
- 1383 Wong, E.K.L., Franza, A., Acikgoz, S., Viggiani, G.M.B., 2021. A Sim-
1384 ple Coupled Analysis of an Arch Bridge Subjected to Tunnelling-Induced
1385 Movements, in: Barla, M., Di Donna, A., Sterpi, D. (Eds.), Challenges
1386 and Innovations in Geomechanics, Proceedings of the 16th International
1387 Conference of IACMAG, Springer International Publishing. pp. 231–238.
1388 doi:[10.1007/978-3-030-64518-2_28](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64518-2_28).
- 1389 Wong, E.K.L., Franza, A., Viggiani, G.M.B., 2025. Empirical prediction of
1390 horizontal movements induced by tunnelling in fine-grained soils. *Canadian
1391 Geotechnical Journal* 62, 1–11. doi:[10.1139/cgj-2024-0049](https://doi.org/10.1139/cgj-2024-0049).
- 1392 Yang, W., Boldini, D., Zhang, D., 2025. Practical implementation of Bi-
1393 Elliptical displacement-controlled method in analysing shallow and large
1394 tunnel excavation impact. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*
1395 158, 106266. doi:[10.1016/j.tust.2024.106266](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2024.106266).
- 1396 Yoo, C., 2013. Interaction between tunneling and bridge foundation – A 3D
1397 numerical investigation. *Computers and Geotechnics* 49, 70–78. doi:[10.
1398 1016/j.compgeo.2012.11.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2012.11.005).
- 1399 Yoo, C., Abbas, Q., 2021. Interaction between two-arch tunnel and pile sup-
1400 ported bridge – An experimental investigation. *Tunnelling and Underground
1401 Space Technology* 112, 103869. doi:[10.1016/j.tust.2021.103869](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2021.103869).